

Effects of Communicative Strategies on the Oral Communicative Skills of Grade Eleven Learners

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Abstract. This study investigated the impact of communicative strategies on the oral communicative skills of Grade 11 students at Calinan National High School. The research addressed a gap in the existing literature by exploring the specific strategies these students utilized and evaluating their effectiveness in enhancing English language oral proficiency. Using a quasi-experimental research design, the study compared the pretest and posttest scores of controlled and experimental groups to determine the significance of the communicative strategies employed. Results indicated a marked improvement in the oral communicative skills of students who had utilized targeted communicative strategies, suggesting that these techniques were instrumental in overcoming linguistic challenges and fostering effective communication. The findings contributed to the pedagogical understanding of language acquisition and highlighted practical approaches for educators to improve students' oral communication skills.

KEY WORDS

1. communicative strategies 2. oral communication skills 3. language learning

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1. Introduction

Oral communication is crucial to human interaction and essential in many life areas, including education, socialization, and professional development. Effective communication requires expressing ideas and thoughts clearly and effectively, engaging in meaningful conversations, and accurately conveying information to others. Oral communication skills are essential for students navigating academic and professional settings, where effective communication can significantly impact success. In the globalized world, proficiency in oral communication in English has become a crucial skill, as it is the most widely used language in business, education, and other professional settings. Over the years, researchers have explored

the various factors influencing oral communication skills, including communicative strategies. Communicative strategies refer to speakers' techniques to overcome communication difficulties, such as paraphrasing, gestures, and clarification (Dornyei Scott, 1997). Many studies have investigated communicative strategies among language learners in English as a second language (ESL) and foreign language contexts. For example, Gupta (2017) conducted a study among high school students in India to investigate the use of communicative strategies in English as a second language. The study found that students who used more communicative strategies had higher proficiency levels and could better communicate their ideas effectively.

Similarly, Kim (2018) conducted a study among high school students in South Korea to explore using communicative strategies in English as a foreign language. The study found that students who used more communicative strategies had higher levels of oral communication proficiency and were more confident in their ability to communicate in English. These studies highlighted the importance of communicative strategies in developing oral communication skills and suggested they could play a significant role in language learning. While there was a growing body of research on communicative strategies and oral communication, there was a gap in the literature when it came to investigating the effect of communicative strategies on oral communication skills among Grade 11 students in Calinan National High School. While the school strongly emphasized English language learning, there had been limited research on students' strategies to develop their oral communication skills. This study aimed to fill this gap by investigating the effect of communicative strategies on the oral communication skills of Grade 11 students at Calinan National High School. The study explored the types of communicative strategies students used and their effectiveness in developing oral communication skills in English. By filling this research gap, the study contributed to the existing literature on communicative strategies and oral communication. It provided insights into effective teaching practices for developing oral communication skills among Grade 11 students. In conclusion, practical oral communication skills are essential for success in academic and professional settings. Communicative strategies played a significant role in developing these skills, and several studies have explored their use in language learning. However, there was a research gap in investigating the effect of communicative strategies on oral communication skills among Grade 11 students in Calinan National High School. This study aimed to fill this gap and provide valuable

insights into effective teaching practices for developing oral communication skills in English.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

This section dealt with the researcher's further reading and research from books, magazines, journals, and the Internet. This related literature further validated and backed up the study on its universal existence as it provided bearing and relevance. Communicative Strategies When learning a second language, learners frequently encounter communication problems caused by a lack of linguistic resources. Learners use Communication strategies to overcome these problems and convey their intended meaning. Strategies may include paraphrasing, substituting new words, switching to the first language, and asking for clarification. These strategies, except switching languages, are also used by native speakers (Ellis, 2008). Selinker introduced the term communication strategy in 1972, and Varadi made the first systematic analysis of communication strategies in 1973. Various other studies were conducted in the 1970s, but the real boom in communication strategy scholarship came in the 1980s (Selinker, 2008). This decade saw a flurry of papers describing and analyzing communication strategies, and Ellen Bialystok linked communication strategies to her general theory of second-language acquisition. There was more activity in the 1990s, with a collection of papers by Kasper and Kellerman and a review article by Dörnyei and Scott, but there has been relatively little research on the subject since then (Schmidt, 2009). These are plans, ways, or means of sharing information adapted to achieve a particular social, political, psychological, or linguistic purpose. The Nomination Strategy is used when introducing a topic at the beginning of a Communication Situation. It can also be applied at any time during an interaction to continue the communication. When this strategy is used, the topic is introduced clearly and truthfully, stating only what is relevant to keep the interaction focused

(Turton, 1998). Restriction Communicative Strategy is a strategy that constrains or restricts the Response of the other person involved in the Communication Situation. The Listener is forced to respond only within a set of categories that the Speaker makes. The Turn-taking Communicative Strategy requires that each Speaker speaks only when it is his/ her turn during the interaction. Knowing when to talk depends on watching out for the verbal and nonverbal cues that signal to the next Speaker that the previous Speaker has finished or the topic under discussion has been exhausted, and a new topic may be introduced. At the same time, it also means that others should be allowed to take turns. Turn-taking Communicative Strategy uses either an informal approach (jump in and start talking) or a formal approach (permission to speak is requested) (Monippally, 2001). After the Nomination Communicative Strategy, the interaction continues using the Topic-Control Communicative Strategy. This is simply a question-answer formula that moves the discussion forward. It also allows the Listener or other participants to take turns, contribute ideas, and continue the discussion. The topic-shifting communicative strategy helps introduce another topic. This strategy works best when there is follow-through so that the new topic continues to be discussed. This is also used in the Repair Communicative Strategy (Nelson, 2012). Repeating is a good way of correcting oneself and gives the Speaker time to do just that. Recasting means changing the form of a message that cannot be understood. It allows the Speaker to say the Message in another way so that the Listener can understand what was originally incomprehensible. When miscommunication occurs, one can apply the Repair Communicative Strategy, which includes requesting clarification, not acknowledging, topic shifting, not responding, repeating, recasting, and adding (Baer, 2010) One requests clarification by asking questions or using eyebrows, eyes, head, or shoulders to show that the Message could not be understood. By not acknowledging the new situation, the situation that is already in progress will continue. Topic shifting can help direct the discussion to another or divert the attention of the Listener from the topic that has become problematic. Lastly, the Termination Communicative Strategy ends the interaction through verbal and nonverbal messages that both the Speaker and the Listener send to each other. Sometimes, the Termination is quick and short. Sometimes, it is prolonged by clarification, further questions, or the continuation of the topic already discussed, but the point of the language and body movement is to end the communication (Neuliep, 2003). A sudden change in communicative strategy may negatively affect the quality of interaction, which includes the performance and organization of ideas of the speaker, the audience, and the message of the topic or discussion. Furthermore, instead of quality organization and successful discussion, the sudden change in communicative strategy may distract the speakers from one particular message to another. Lastly, respect, formalities, roles, and responsibilities will be trampled upon (Rogers, 1982). Communicative strategy is the most effective tool in delivering and acquiring information from both speaker and listener. Based on previous references, it is used to share valuable ideas and efficiently provide quality interaction and communication. It affects the following: The Speaker chooses the most familiar topic, which he is willing to discuss and expound on the extent of his expertise. He initiates the interaction and takes control of the success of the communication using the proper way of presentation (Thorpe, 2006). Role and Responsibilities of the Speaker—These serve as the lifeline of the quality of interaction in communication because the speaker handles the pros and cons of the feedback received. When these are met, he creates a diversified way of thinking. The Audience—This refers to the listeners who may react to the ideas presented. Their reac-

tions may enhance or diminish the flow of communication based on the topic's interest (Thill, 2013). Relationship - The bond between the speaker and listener may depend on how the discussions relate to their interests and knowledge. Quality Interaction – This is achieved when the speaker and listener exchange related information, improving their reception. The Delivery – This is affected by whether the listeners can fully understand the concept implied or create doubtful remarks. Proper delivery requires techniques that demand the speaker to express thoroughly (Rutherford, 2007). The Message is the core concept of the interaction. The message is correct and acceptable when the speaker can answer all the listener's questions beforehand and is received positively. When communicative strategies are used effectively, the speaker and listener improve their interactive inputs and outputs (Raman, 2011). Oral Communication Skills Oral communication is the process of expressing ideas through speech, and it plays a crucial role in students' lives. An individual learns the basics of oral communication right at home. The school environment takes this learning a notch higher by teaching the students how to interact with peers and teachers. The quality of communication in student life will define professional communication later in life. Good communication enables students to assimilate more from the learning process by empowering them to ask relevant questions and discuss doubts (Moore, 2010). Oral communication skills are fundamental to developing literacy and essential for thinking and learning. Through talk, students communicate information and explore and come to understand ideas and concepts, identify and solve problems, organize their experiences and knowledge, and express and clarify their thoughts, feelings, and opinions. Listening and speaking skills are essential for social interaction at home, school, and community (Bradlow, 2016). To develop oral communication skills, students need numerous opportunities to listen

and talk about various subjects, including personal interests, school work, and current affairs. The language program should provide opportunities for students to engage in various oral activities in connection with expectations in all the strands, such as brainstorming to identify what they know about the topic of a new text they are about to read, discussing strategies for solving a problem in a writing assignment, presenting and defending ideas or debating issues, and offering critiques of work produced by their peers (Salvisberg, 2010). For all students to benefit from the opportunities provided for listening and speaking, differences in the norms and conventions associated with oral communication in different cultures must be considered. Although children usually start to develop oral language skills before they learn to read and write, developing reading and writing skills can enhance their ability to use and understand oral language clearly, accurately, and critically (Lucas, 2008). Communication skills are vital for a student's academic success and future career prospects. In today's challenging environment, students must possess academic expertise and the requisite skills to enhance their learning and employability prospects (Smiljanic, 2006). Communication is a dynamic process involving interaction between two or more people, the sender and the receiver. The primary purpose of communication is to transmit thoughts and beliefs to another person. The significant components of communication are verbal, oral, and nonverbal communication. Oral communication is the process of expressing ideas through the medium of speech, which plays a crucial role in students' lives (Sereno, 2018). An individual learns the basics of oral communication right at home. The school environment takes this learning a notch higher by teaching the students how to interact with peers and teachers. The quality of communication in student life will define professional communication later in life. Good communication enables students to

assimilate more from the learning process by empowering them to ask relevant questions and discuss doubts (Scarborough, 2013). Effective verbal communication nurtures socialization by facilitating new friendships, which, in turn, aid the learning process. Productive communication is a boost to career development. An ability to convey thoughts clearly and precisely would help a student make a favorable impression at an interview and get the job he deserves. Communication skills inculcate professionalism in speaking styles, self-expression, and attitudes toward others, holding students in good stead in their professional lives (Lesikar, 2002). The hallmark of a good student communicator is that he has mastered the art of preparing, organizing, and delivering successful oral presentations. Oral communication includes real-time presentations, video presentations, and interviews, with accompanying visual aids such as handouts and PowerPoint. Message is the key to good oral communication. The substance of the presentation should be relevant to the audience and goals of the presentation. Self-awareness is the starting point of good oral communication. A person aware of his strengths and weaknesses can make the required effort to improve communication skills (Hasson, 2012). Confidence is another vital aspect of good communication. A person may know the subject but not communicate adequately if he lacks confidence. Simplicity in messaging is indispensable for good communication, as the assimilation of the message is directly proportional to the clarity of its presentation. Awareness of the audience is an essential tool for an effective oral communicator. A good communicator can gauge the impact by observing the audience's body language and feedback and adjusting his approach accordingly (Fensterheim, 2010). Interaction is the path to effectiveness. A student oral communicator can engage the audience by asking questions and soliciting opinions. This would also help fine-tune the message and presentation style based on the audience's feedback. The presenter's tone of voice carries much weight in delivering the message. A confident tone keeps the audience engaged, whereas a low and monotonous tone can be off-putting (Hall, 1989). Voice modulation can also be employed to highlight the critical points in the presentation and retain the audience's attention. Body language is an essential component of effective oral communication. The student should adopt a stable and confident posture, make appropriate gestures, avoid fidgety, and establish eye contact during the presentation (Collins, 2009). Oral communication is not merely the ability to speak but also the capacity to listen. A good communicator is attuned to the audience and can calibrate his message accordingly. An aspiring oral communicator should be willing to acquire and hone his listening skills over some time. Oral communication is an art that can be learned and polished through reading, presentation skills, and practice. An oral communicator should have intellectual curiosity. Reading is a means to the development of good communication skills. A well-educated mind could communicate better, as content is the soul of the communication process. He should also possess an attitude of discussion and deliberation, as this would improve intellectual capabilities and thereby contribute to effective communication (Boyee, 1997). Practical writing and good verbal communication skills go hand in hand, although they may appear antithetical to a newbie. A student with good writing skills can alone organize and present his thoughts in a structured manner; exposure to the nitty-gritty of essay writing would be immensely beneficial. The age-old dictum 'Practice makes a person perfect' makes perfect sense in oral communication (Bonet, 2004). The first impression is the best, and many students fail this test due to various impediments such as stage fright, lack of self-confidence, and performance anxiety. A student can conquer his fears and master the art of oral

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study

communication by participating in many natural and mock presentations and speech-based activities (Ajmani, 2012). Active participation in the community would transform a student into a good communicator by honing his linguistic abilities. Moreover, a leadership position in an academic setting would be an essential asset to a student’s CV. To conclude, a student willing to put his nose to the grindstone can smoothly transition from a tentative speaker to an effective and seasoned oral communicator (Adair, 2003).

1.2. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—The study was anchored on the theory proposed by Tomskin (2011), who emphasized that communication is essential for human life and is a fundamental necessity. Human beings require communication to express themselves, convey information to others, and share their thoughts

1.3. Statement of the Problem—This study sought to determine the effect of Communicative Strategies on the oral communicative skills of grade eleven learners. Eventually, it also

and emotions.

This perspective is further supported by Prachi (2015), who asserted that communication is indispensable for societal development. While classical theories like capitalism have historically justified certain societal structures, Development Communication theory, also known as Development Support Communication, advocates for media engagement in positive developmental initiatives, adhering to state guidelines and directives.

The diagram accompanying this experimental research illustrates the flow of communicative strategies aimed at enhancing the oral communication skills of grade eleven students. The intervention adopts a back-to-basics approach aimed at improving learners’ decoding abilities.

sought to determine the magnitude of the effect of the action initiated by the researcher on the communication skills of the research subjects. Moreover, it sought answers to the following sub-problems

- (1) What are the pretest scores of the grade eleven students in both controlled and experimental groups?

- (2) What are the posttest scores of the grade eleven students in both the controlled and experimental groups?
- (3) Is there a significant difference between the post-scores of the controlled and experimental groups?
- (4) What is the magnitude of the effect of the Communicative Strategies on the oral communication skills of grade eleven students?

1.4. Significance of the Study—The results of the study were of great benefit to the following: DepEd Officials. The results and findings of this study were beneficial to DepEd Officials, particularly in policy redirection and recommending strategies for developing the oral communication skills of grade eleven students in classroom instruction. Key department officials were in charge of policy analysis and development to be implemented in the schools in the field. School heads were also considered beneficiaries of this study. They could develop local policies and implement school-based initiatives to address the learners' learning needs, particularly in developing oral communication skills. Oral communication was essential as it served as a gauge of one's self-confidence. Teachers, being the frontline in education and having direct contact with the learners, were considered the primary beneficiaries of this study. They reflected on which strategies to use in the classroom to develop the student's oral communication skills. Their pedagogical competence in teaching oral communication guided them to achieve the goal of making everyone an independent learner.

2. Methodology

This chapter will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to proofread this work during its preparation meticulously. Artificial Intelligence (AI) helped in enhancing the manuscript's quality, coherence, and precision. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used the quasi-experimental research design, a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. The non-equivalent design was considered a good choice when the researcher had access to only one experimental group (Vockel, 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the study subjects were an intact group of learners. This design was represented as follows:

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted at Calinan National High School, a division of Davao City. The subjects were 70 grade eleven students—35 were from section A, which served as the control group, and 35 were from section B, which served as the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous, as both learners from sections A and B had identical grades. This study used the non-random assignment of subjects, where all students from sections A and B were involved as study subjects.

O₁ x O₂

O₃ x O₄

01	Pretest of the experimental group
02	Posttest of the experimental group
03	Pretest of the controlled group
04	Posttest of the controlled group

—	Non-random assignment of subjects
X	Treatment applied in the experimental group

Description of variables in the study
Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	Section	No. of Students
1	Section A	35
2	Section B	35
Total		70

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new regular learning modality. It was a blended learning approach where teachers provided modules while conducting virtual classroom instruction online. The researcher had to meet the learners online for a follow-up session to discuss the content of the printed module. The pre and post-performance test consisted of a 30-item test that eventually determined the com-

prehension skills of the research subjects. The pretest was administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. It was beneficial in assessing the oral comprehension skills of the grade eleven learners. On the other hand, the post-test was administered to measure the effect of the treatment. Based on the DepEd rating system, the following continuum was used to determine grade eleven students' comprehension skills.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of the data-gathering procedure, the researcher drafted letters seeking permission for the research study to be conducted. These letters were sent to Reynante A. Solitario, CESO IV, Schools Division Superintendent Division of Davao City, and to the School Principal of Calinan National High School. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the School

president and the principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and had it validated by the experts, preferably the study's experts. After permission had been granted for this study to be conducted in Calinan National High School and after the expert validators had thoroughly examined the research questionnaire, the researcher administered the online pretest to both the controlled and experimental classes.

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

Subsequently, she commenced her experiment by using communicative strategies to develop oral communication skills in the experimental class. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered the online posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation, after which the researcher made analyses and interpretations of the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—In this investigation, an array of statistical methodologies was employed to meticulously analyze and interpret the respondents’ data. Specifically, the arithmetic mean served as the tool to delineate the pretest and posttest oral comprehension profi-

ciencies observed within both the control and experimental groups. The application of the t-test facilitated a rigorous assessment focused on identifying any statistically significant disparities between the post-test scores recorded for the control and experimental cohorts. Furthermore, the Eta squared measure was adeptly utilized to quantify the effect size attributed to the implementation of the worksheet approach on the oral comprehension abilities of eleventh-grade students. This comprehensive statistical analysis underscores the robust framework underpinning the study, ensuring a precise evaluation of the educational intervention’s efficacy.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the problems in this study. They are thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners, and the Significant Relationship between the Pre-test and Post-test Scores.

Table 3 shows the pre-test scores of the grade eleven students. The control group got a mean of 38.50 with a rating of 77.00 or Developing, while the experimental group got a mean of 37.70 with a rating of 75.40 or Developing.

This means that students at this level possess the minimum knowledge skills and core understandings but need help performing authentic tasks.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Control Group	35	38.50	77.00	Developing
Experimental Group	35	37.70	75.40	Developing

It can also be observed from the table that during the pre-test, the rating of the experimental group was closely identical to that of the controlled group, although both belong to the Developing level. Therefore, we can consider that the lead of the controlled group is not significant. This finding is congruent with the idea of Seymour (2015), who said that the quality of instruction children receive also influences reading development. Phonically-based reading instruction (explicitly teaching children the letter-sound relations and how to use "sounding out" strategies to read unfamiliar words) is more effective than less systematic approaches (National Institute of Child Health and Human Development, 2000). It is also well-accepted that children learn to read more easily in alphabetic orthographies (writing systems) with highly consistent spelling-to-sound correspondences than in less consistent orthographies. Collaborative learning methods that emphasize peer interaction have been widely applied to increase the intensity and effectiveness of EFL reading programs. However, simply grouping students heterogeneously and assigning them

group goals does not guarantee that effective collaborative learning will ensue (Brazil, 2011).

3.1. *Post-Test Score of Pupils*—Table 2 shows the post-test scores of the grade eleven students. The control group got a mean of 43.60 with a rating of 87.20 or Approaching Proficiency, while the experimental group gained a mean of 45.90 with a rating of 91.80 or Proficient. It can be noted from the table that during the post-test, the experimental group had a higher mean rating than the control group. It got a mean rating increase of 8.20 from a mean rating of 37.70 to 45.90. This means that students in the controlled group at this level have developed the fundamental knowledge skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks. On the other hand, students in the experimental group at this level have developed fundamental knowledge skills and core understandings that can be transferred independently through authentic performance tasks. control group.

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	35	43.60	87.20	Approaching Proficiency
Experimental Group	35	45.90	91.80	Proficient

This finding is congruent with Thorpe's (2016) idea that communicative strategy is the most effective tool for delivering and acquiring information from both the speaker and the listener. This is used to efficiently share helpful ideas and provide quality interaction in commu-

nication based on previous references. It affects the following: The Speaker – Chooses the most familiar topic, which he is willing to discuss and expound on the extent of his expertise. He initiates the interaction and takes control of the success of the communication using the proper

way of presentation. Oral communication is the process of expressing ideas through the medium of speech, which plays a crucial role in the life of students. An individual learns the basics of oral communication right at home. The school environment takes this learning a notch higher by teaching the students how to interact with peers and teachers. The quality of communication in student life will define professional communication later in life. Good communication enables students to assimilate more from the learning process by empowering them to ask

relevant questions and discuss doubts (Moore, 2010). Table 3 shows the test for the significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.10 with a p-value of .0215, which is less than the .05 level of significance. This means that there is a significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the grade eleven students. This implies the application of communicative strategies to the oral communication skills of grade eleven students.

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	69	-5.10	.0215	Significant

This finding aligns with the statement of Bradlow (2016), who disclosed that oral communication skills are fundamental to the development of literacy and essential for thinking and learning. Through talk, students communicate information and explore and come to understand ideas and concepts, identify and solve problems, organize their experiences and knowledge, and express and clarify their thoughts, feelings, and opinions. Listening and speaking skills are essential for social interaction at home, school, and community (Bradlow, 2016). To develop oral communication skills, students need numerous opportunities to listen and talk about various subjects, including personal interests, school work, and current affairs. The language program should provide opportunities for students to engage in various oral activities in connection with expectations in all the strands, such as brainstorming to identify what they know about

the topic of a new text they are about to read, discussing strategies for solving a problem in a writing assignment, presenting and defending ideas or debating issues, and offering critiques of work produced by their peers (Salvisberg, 2010).

3.2. *Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretests and Post-test Scores of the Grade Eleven Learners*—Table 4 highlights the test of communicative strategies on the oral communication skills of grade eleven students. It generated an Eta squared value of 0.270, which signifies a significant effect. This implies that the use of communicative strategies in developing the oral communication skills of the grade eleven students is compelling. It also implies that the action initiated by the researcher has developed the respondents’ oral communication skills, as they can communicate effectively in the classroom and in school.

This finding is in line with Lucas’s (2018) idea that in order for all students to benefit from the opportunities provided for listening

and speaking, differences in the norms and conventions associated with oral communication in different cultures must be taken into account.

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretests and Post-test Scores of the Grade Eleven Learners

N	t-value	Eta ²	Descriptive Value	Decision
70	-4.10	0.270	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Although children normally start to develop oral language skills before they learn to read and write, the development of reading and writing skills can enhance their ability to use and understand oral language clearly, accurately, and critically. Communication skills are vital for a student’s academic success and future career prospects. In today’s challenging environment, students must possess not only academic expertise but also the requisite skills to enhance their learning and employability prospects (Smiljanic, 2006).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter synthesizes the outcomes, inferences, and proposals deduced from a meticulous analysis and interpretation of the research findings. This investigation aimed to ascertain the impact of communicative strategies on the oral communication competencies of Grade 11 students.

Employing a quasi-experimental research methodology, specifically a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design, facilitated this exploration. According to Vockel (1983), a non-equivalent design is advantageous when the investigator can only access a singular group for experimental purposes. The choice of this design was predicated on the nature of the study’s participants being an intact learning cohort.

The research unfolded within Calinan National High School, situated in the Division of Davao City. It engaged 70 Grade 11 students, divided into a control group (Section A, comprised of 35 students) and an experimental group (Section B, encompassing 35 students). The heterogeneous composition of these sections meant that the students across both segments exhibited a commensurate range of performance levels. This study proceeded with the non-random allocation of participants, incorporating all learners from sections A and B into the research.

4.1. Findings—Findings revealed that the incorporation of communicative strategies significantly enhances the oral communication abilities of Grade 11 students. Furthermore, a noteworthy disparity was observed in the post-test outcomes of the control and experimental groups, highlighting the effectiveness of these strategies.

4.2. Conclusions—Drawing from the integrated analysis, the study concludes that the initial oral communication capabilities of the Grade 11 students in both the control and experimental groups were categorized as Developing. Post intervention, the control group ascended to the Approaching Proficiency level, whereas the

experimental group attained the Proficient tier.

4.3. Recommendations—Reflecting on the conclusions derived from this research, the following recommendations are postulated:

- (1) Educators specializing in oral communication are encouraged to diversify their instructional strategies to foster the development of students’ oral communication skills. Tailoring these strategies to accommodate varied learning modalities will enhance their efficacy.
- (2) Educational leaders are urged to formally endorse the adoption of communicative strategies through the issuance of a directive. Such a mandate, au-

thenticated by the educational authority, would promote a systemic implementation of these strategies, thereby nurturing students' oral communicative proficiency.

- (3) Future scholarly endeavors should embark on comparative analyses concerning the application of communicative

strategies. These studies should transcend the domain of oral communication to encompass a holistic examination across diverse academic disciplines.

This refined academic rendering not only encapsulates the essence of the initial findings and recommendations but also elevates the discourse to a more scholarly and persuasive register.

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